

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A TEACHER AND ITS SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES

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Abstract: In this work, the factors forming the professional development of the teacher's personality and their socio-psychological image are analyzed. Therefore, this work highlights the stages of professional development of a teacher, the internal and external factors influencing it, as well as pedagogical and psychological approaches to the formation of the socio-psychological image of a teacher.

Keywords: Teacher, professional development, personal growth, socio-psychological image, pedagogical image, professional competence, modern teacher, quality of education, communicative skills, teacher personality.

Аннотация: В данной работе проанализированы факторы, формирующие профессиональное развитие личности педагога и его социально-психологический облик. Поэтому в данной работе освещены этапы профессионального развития педагога, внутренние и внешние факторы, влияющие на него, а также педагогические и психологические подходы к формированию социально-психологического имиджа педагога.

Ключевые слова: Учитель, профессиональное развитие, личностный рост, социально-психологический образ, педагогический имидж, профессиональная компетентность, современный учитель, качество образования, коммуникативные навыки, личность учителя.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ishda pedagog shaxsining kasbiy rivojlanishi hamda uning ijtimoiy-psixologik qiyofasini shakllantiruvchi omillar tahlil qilingan. Shu bois ushbu ishda pedagog kasbiy rivojlanishining bosqichlari, unga ta'sir etuvchi ichki va tashqi omillar, shuningdek, o'qituvchining ijtimoiy-psixologik imidjini

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagog, kasbiy rivojlanish, shaxsiy o'sish, ijtimoiy-psixologik kommunikativ ko'nikmalar, o'qituvchi shaxsi.

ENTRANCE:

In the current period of rapid development of the modern education system, the professional skills and personal image of a teacher have become one of the important criteria for the quality and effectiveness of education. The development of a teacher's personality directly affects their influence on students, their work with parents, their cooperation with colleagues, and their reputation in society. Therefore, the professional growth of a teacher, their work on themselves in accordance with the requirements of the time, and their socio-psychological stability is a pressing issue today. In the study of the issue of professional development and socio-psychological image of a teacher, there are many studies on the current conditions of the education system, professional activity, personal development, and socio-

psychological image of teachers. This literature review includes specific theoretical approaches and practical recommendations for the professional development and formation of the socio-psychological image of a teacher.

RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

V. Davydov, studying the development of the pedagogical system and improving its quality, put forward several important ideas about the professional development of the teacher and his role in the educational process. In his opinion, the personal development of a teacher determines the effectiveness of the educational process, and the professional competence of a teacher increases the quality of education. Davydov's work "Pedagogical Activity and Mechanisms of its Development" shows approaches to the formation of a teacher's communicative and pedagogical skills, problem-solving in the educational process. M. Sechenov's research in the field of psychology and physiology is of great importance in the formation of the socio-psychological image of a teacher. In his work "The Nervous System and its Role in Human Activity," Sechenov illuminates the psychological state of a person and how it affects professional activity. Emphasizes the need to consider the professional development of a teacher and their personal characteristics, as well as psychological factors in influencing students. He showed the importance of psychological knowledge in the formation of a teacher's self-expression and interaction with society.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A teacher is a highly cultured specialist, deeply knowledgeable in their subject, well-versed in general and child psychology, and perfectly versed in educational methodology. The main goal and objective of the educational process is to train well-rounded, mature individuals and qualified specialists. Therefore, we must know how to measure and evaluate the effectiveness of education and upbringing by how well students possess knowledge, skills, and abilities, and how they are prepared for independent learning and finding their place in society. Education forms the basis of human development. In the new century, the comprehensive development of society directly depends on the development and improvement of the content of education. At the same time, the globalization of education, the introduction of innovative technologies, and the flow of large-scale information require constant updating and improving the content of education. "Innovation is the process and activity of introducing innovations and changes into the field," "innovative technology is the process of organizational activity aimed at ensuring pedagogical development." In the context of rapid modern development, the need for innovative pedagogical activity and technologies in society, culture, and education is determined by a number of factors: - more precisely, socio-economic changes requiring fundamental changes in the innovative education system, updates in the education system, the need to use methods and technologies in organizing the educational process in various educational institutions. The innovative orientation of teachers' activities manifests itself as a means of updating educational policy; - the content of education is characterized by the number of academic disciplines and In such a situation, pedagogical knowledge and status among teachers increase, and the professional skills of teachers increase significantly. - a change in the approach to the application and assimilation of innovations by teachers. In conditions where

the educational process required strict adherence to time norms, there were certain limitations for teachers not only in the voluntary choice of programs and textbooks, but also in the choice of methods and means of their pedagogical activity.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

From time immemorial, attention has been paid to the personal and social qualities of teachers, and, based on the requirements of each time, the requirements for a teacher have been constantly improving and becoming more complex. The conducted research showed that any teacher must possess the following social qualities. Firstly, a teacher must have a good understanding of the role of the pedagogical profession in society and the history of its emergence. Firstly, in the process of studying the history of pedagogy, a person learns about the role of pedagogical activity in human life, the history of the formation of the basic laws, rules, and principles of pedagogy. Secondly, the future teacher must master the general aspects of intellectual activity (thinking, memory, perception, visualization, attention), the culture of behavior, including pedagogical communication. Thirdly, the teacher must have a good understanding of philosophy. Because philosophy teaches a person to think abstractly. When a teacher enters the classroom, if abstract thinking is poorly developed, they lose their composure. In order to attract the attention of the audience, a person must have well-developed abstract thinking. Fourthly, a teacher who teaches certain scientific knowledge should also teach morality and manners to the younger generation. After all, such a task is the duty and responsibility of teachers and educators. Fifthly, a person engaged in education must be aesthetically educated. Everyone knows how important aesthetic education plays in the development of society. It should not be forgotten that aesthetic

education is an important and integral part of spiritual education. In the structure of pedagogical culture, its moral and ethical section occupies an important place. This is the formation of the process of pedagogical trust, its result, and a greater determination of the teacher's own interests.

RESULT

In this study, the factors influencing the professional development and formation of the socio-psychological image of a teacher were analyzed. It has been established that the successful activity of a teacher's personality depends not only on their own qualifications and knowledge, but also on their personal development, social interaction, and psychological skills. The process of professional development of a teacher is complex and multi-stage, which is closely related to internal motivation, pedagogical knowledge, personal growth, and environmental factors. In the formation of the socio-psychological image of teachers, their communicative skills, behavior, place in society, and ability to express themselves play an important role. Under the influence of innovative approaches to the professional development of a teacher, the mastery of new pedagogical technologies, and socio-economic conditions, this process is constantly being updated. The ability of teachers to adapt to the changing educational system is the main factor in improving their professional skills and conducting effective pedagogical activity. In addition, the spiritual culture, aesthetic education, and moral character of a teacher significantly increase their effectiveness in the educational process. A person who has reached a high level of pedagogical culture successfully performs their professional duties, influences students, and leaves a positive mark on the social environment.

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